

Electronic Surveillance

Gauri Phadtare, Anushree Goud

Bharti Vidyapeeth's Institute of Management and Information Technology (BVMIT)
Mumbai, Maharashtra, India

ABSTRACT

There have been research on the CCTV (closed circuit television) for safety purpose as an investigative tool. Using CCTV was associated with very significantly increased chance of crime have been solved for all crime types. Evidences like images are most likely used to catch the person who did the crime, the usefulness of CCTV is limited by several factors, mostly the public areas are not covered. This research paper is on all about how CCTV has been useful for humans for secure and safety purpose. Electronic Surveillance features of society globally, this paper also focus on healthcare context. This paper is based on what I have researched while searching topic on Electronics Surveillance.

Keywords: *Surveillance Studies, Electronics, Information Technology, Surveillance.*

I. INTRODUCTION

These system consist of cameras with monitors and video recorders. The cameras may be fixed range or less pixel of quality. But nowadays cameras have been developing quality like now they have pan, tilt, zoom which can use as per need of persons. Image and video captured and stored and also retrieved anytime in future. The quality of the equipment used is a chief determinant of outcomes. The positioning is also important for maximum security for covering large area and comes under safety. All these factors need to be taken care while installing the CCTV surveillance system at that particular place.[1]

If you want to keep your home safe, electronic surveillance can monitor what is happening in your home even while you are away. The same applies to a place of business. A combination of video and audio

surveillance gives you the most complete picture of what is happening at a specific place and time.[2] It is a way to oversee behavior, activity, and information for the purpose of protecting, managing, or influencing a certain location.

Surveillance is used by governments for intelligence gathering, prevention of crime, the protection of a process, person, group or object, or the investigation of crime. It is also used by criminal organizations to plan and commit crimes, such as robbery and kidnapping, by businesses to gather intelligence.

A criminal investigation can be think as serious question like; what happen exactly behind them and who was involved in the crime, where did it happen, when did it took place, and anyone get harmed or not. It plays the important role to catch any incident happen in absence of that person.[1][2]

While researching on this topic “Electronic Surveillance” I got to know that surveillance is not limited to watch over on any one or any place under surveillance of cameras but it is also the meaning that any observant that if any thing related to health can be detected by perfect observation on that particular place or area.

There are some example on it one of them are listed below:

EXAMPLE:

Every one know that electronic surveillance may use as technology to gather data the purposes of that surveillance, but here case is different; Internet search engines are mostly used for searching some sort of related data, like if somebody had any type of illness

rather to go doctor they first search on GOOGLE for the remedy so they can use and have some temporary relief on that illness.[3]

When some people gets the symptoms of illness the first thing they do is search the remedy on GOOGLE. [3]GOOGLE has masses of up to date data of their visitors. The medication and information for specific illness searching, by analyzing the terms that person use for relevant specific symptoms, like some particular area at particular time then it can find that some sort of illness in that area and by tracking their performance healthcare can be provided before any thing serious can happen.

Such kind of partice can use for tracking dengue, HIV or some kind of major illness spreading in that area. The advantage of this type is that it allows for rapid detection and prediction of illness in area so precaution can be provided at that time

II Scope

The main objective of this document is to make people aware that what is the technique they are using and what are methods which are behind to the logic and what does make CCTV help in the real life. These Consist of great technology along with the some algorithms which make it so very much useful in the market and also very demanding these days.

Many times the cameras are assumed to do job of everything that can be recorded and particular incidents can be viewed based on the offences that just happened when that person is not around in area. If person wants to see what happens behind him/her on that particular location then he/she can put the CCTV and for some time they can rely on the CCTV and then after they can retrieved the images or videos of what happen in absences.[1][3]

III Literature Survey

The survey has been seen that some time CCTV cannot be so helpful as people think, it can be used as the purpose to keep watch on particular person at any time and from any where.

The problem like;

Any person can keep camera or any video device just to watch that person to what doing or what activity they do at their place.

Cyber crime any video device including CCTV can be hack or can be destroyed by using some device which can stop that recording or make some disturbance while recording the any particular incident.[4]

Some kind of people can use such device just to earn some money by using their personal video and by blackmailing them.

As per the device is used their maintains cost also increases, some people can't afford such highly technique device and adjust on affordable device and then device cant capture properly image or images can get blur while zoom in.

Such problems can arises while we uses the CCTV.

IV Existing system

The system nowadays are used in places are highly developed and used for avoiding or catching the anyone who does some action on their absence. Now the system have moving face monitor like in front of them person moves from left to right them monitor or camera also move with them, so camera moves so the range also gets wider and camera can see a lot more than still cameras.

They have zoom in movement also where it can zoom in at that particular place and capture the image ,lot of high techniques are develop in this field.

Existing system can save the place from crime and lots of incident can be avoided if many of public or private place have CCTV at their place.

It can be better proof for investigation purpose, and using better quality of device can give lots of benefits for safety.[3][4]

V Working

The working of CCTV is very simple but in care-full way[4];

1.First think or search such a place from where large area can get under the eye of camera and then set the CCTV over there, stores them in the data.

2. Second think see how much the camera can catch the range and quality of camera so after the incident or ant thing happened that time image and video can be see clearly.

3. Keep the CCTV for safety purpose only not for any illegal reason.

4. Keep CCTV always on and recording mode cause some people think just keeping CCTV on standby mode criminal can get scare and they can't do anything, but some people can be smart also.

5. Major think keep CCTV camera in such a place so no one can catch the CCTV and you can catch them easily.

VI Conclusion

In conclusion most of public places or private places must have CCTV for there safety perspective. They must have security if their local areas are not good, so

to avoid the crimes like kidnapping, robbery, murders, etc can reduce at least ground level.

VII Reference

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